

Microwave Assisted Alternate Synthesis of a Series of Azomethine Derivatives of a Presently Prescribing Semisynthetic Aminopenicillin (Amoxicillin)

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ABSTRACT

The field of synthesis of organic compounds always incorporates different possible methods for achieving the target compounds. The methods adopted for synthesis must be routed firmly to the green principles in a maximum possible manner. This paper aims the microwave assisted synthesis of a series of azomethine derivatives of widely prescribing semisynthetic penicillin drug called amoxicillin. The microwave assisted synthesis of organic compounds is considered as one of the safest among green methods of the synthesis. For the synthesis of azomethines a series of aromatic aldehydes with varying substituent groups and the drug amoxicillin trihydrate were irradiated using microwave as the source of energy.

Keyword: Amoxicillin; MWAOS; Computer aided Drug designing; Biological activity; Computational methods; Docking

INTRODUCTION

The field of drug research is always introduces novel methods for the synthesis of drug or drug like molecules and microwave heating is the superior among other methods[1,2]. Recently the use of microwave ovens for the organic synthesis is getting a boom in our country. Many researchers and groups of many universities and institutions are found actively engaged in MAWOS. Microwaves have wavelengths of 1mm-1m, corresponding to frequencies between 0.3 and 300GHz. In order to avoid interference, the wavelength at which the industrial and domestic microwave apparatus intended for heating operations is regulated generally to 12.2cm, corresponding to a frequency of 2.450(+/- 0.050)GHz. It has been known for quite a long time that microwaves can be used to heat materials to a considerable extent. The microwave technology has been used since the late 1970s, in inorganic chemistry but it has only been implemented in organic chemistry since the mid-1980s and now became a widely using research technique. It could be due to its lack of controllability and reproducibility faced during the synthesis along with many safety aspects and a generally low degree of understanding of the basics of dielectric heating of microwaves that is introduced into the chemical reactor remotely which has a direct access to the reaction control as it being the main energy source applied to the reaction vessel. The microwave radiation passes through the walls of the reaction vessel and heats only the reactants and solvents in a uniform manner throughout the reaction and causes lesser byproducts. The reduced possibility of byproducts formation made it one of the greener methods with a prime importance. Microwaves also simplified many complicated methods and reduced the use of many solvents and also triggered techniques like solvent free organic synthesis. The microwave techniques have now been realized in several synthetic operations such as

protection and deprotection, condensation, oxidation, reduction, cyclization, rearrangement reactions and rapid synthesis of heterocyclic system on solid supports [3].

Many of the scientists are trying to redesign the synthesis, the most attracting field of chemistry to more environmentally benign approach by adopting many plausible concepts of green chemistry. There are many available reviews and research papers on MWAOS in the scientific literatures that concentrate on the derivatives and synthesis of many biologically active compounds (like Schiff bases and β - lactams) at the amino group [4a-d]. The drug resistance is one of the most challenging problems that faced by the drug researchers all over the world. The easiest remedy for overcoming this hurdle is the suitable derivatisation of the presently prescribing drugs [5]. In this paper simple microwave assisted synthesis of derivatives of a leadingly prescribing aminopenicillin namely amoxicillin (Scheme 1).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials used for this synthesis were a series of substituted aromatic aldehydes (Sigma Aldrich make) and the drug amoxicillin trihydrate (physician's sample). The reactants were used as such without any further purification. The uses of purified solvents were limited to a minimum. The experimental techniques were carried out in a domestic microwave oven of (Samsung make). Computational methods were carried out in on a Windows Vista Business based system with Genuine Intel (R) CPU T2050 1.60GHz 512 MB of memory. Molecular modelling was achieved by MOPAC and docking studies were carried out in ArgusLab4.0.1 as reported earlier. The antibacterial studies were carried out on β -lactamase producing bacteria using the drug (amoxicillin) as the standard.

Experimental

The equimolar mixture of the drug (amoxicillin) and the substituted aromatic aldehyde mixed thoroughly in a glass mortar. It is Moistened with basic methanol and transferred to a 25mL glass beaker immersed on a silica bath and irradiated with microwave. The changes were recorded and the irradiations were stopped immediately when visible colour change appeared. The time needed for the derivative formation varies with different starting materials. The derivatives obtained were cooled and crushed in a mortar and further purified using common methods. The systematic characterizations of the synthesized derivatives were carried out by UV, FT-IR and NMR. Molecular masses were studied using simple cryoscopy. The results were compared with theoretically predicted results of computational studies of various methods like AM1, MNDO, MNDO/3 and PM3.

The drug and its different derivatives of the drugs were coded as D1, D1S1, D1S2, D1S3, D1S4, D1S5 and D1S6 for easy usage.

The D1S1 is found reported using conventional method and comparable to the MW-method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The NMR spectra were recorded in DMSO-D₆ and found much complicated to interpret completely but the shift of NH proton attached to the lactam ring was found to be more and more deshielded and shifts to higher δ -values in all the derivatives than parent drug. The -NH₂ protons were found absent in the derivatives and the deshielded -N=CH protons in the derivative are clearly observed in higher δ -values [6]. All the spectra were showing characteristic peaks of COOH around 9-10ppm and vanished in presence of few drops of D₂O. The predicted vibration spectral (infra red) data using different computational methods like AM1, MNDO, MNDO/3 and PM3 were comparable with the actual spectral data observed (Table 1).

D1S1 is	R ¹ =OH	R ² =R ³ =R ⁴ =R ⁵ =H
D1S2 is	R ¹ =NO ₂	R ² =R ³ =R ⁴ =R ⁵ =H
D1S3 is	R ² =NO ₂	R ¹ =R ³ =R ⁴ =R ⁵ =H
D1S4 is	R ³ =N(CH ₃) ₂	R ¹ =R ² =R ⁴ =R ⁵ =H
D1S5 is	R ³ =OH; R ⁴ =O(CH ₃)	R ¹ =R ² =R ⁵ =H
And		
D1S6 is	R ³ =OH	R ¹ =R ² =R ⁴ =R ⁵ =H

Scheme 1: Various derivatives of the drug prepared by Microwave irradiation method.

Table 1: Calculated and plausibly assigned vibrational frequencies of drug and its derivatives.

Derivative	Functional Group	Vibrational Frequency Calculated and Observed and Assigned (CM ⁻¹)					
		AM1	MNDO	MNDO/3	PM3	Average	Observed
D1	OH	3454.75	3985.22	3954.76	3887.16	3820.473	3457.53
	NH ₂	3346.32	3397.28	3394.17	3400.35	3384.53	3162.64
	C=O LACT.	2027.81	2110.93	1834.77	1965.07	1984.645	1775.35
	C=O	1969.53	2059.10	1822.98	1889.33	1935.235	1686.47
D1S2	OH	3461.97	3958.16	3955.43	3882.29	3814.463	3408.22
	N=C	1940.64	2224.59	2002.20	2003.53	2042.74	1633.00
	C=O LACT.	1995.38	2305.87	2002.20	2008.01	2077.865	1730.00
	C=O	1965.22	2124.62	1832.25	1857.69	1944.945	1607.00
D1S3	OH	3457.65	3970.26	3983.5	3886.87	3824.57	3418
	N=C	2002.99	1946.08	1758.26	1915.63	1905.74	1528
	C=O LACT.	2026.41	2106.30	1831.92	1946.06	1977.673	1742.00
	C=O	1989.59	2078.22	1814.95	1915.63	1949.598	1649.00
D1S4	OH	3457.02	3983.35	3952.51	3886.21	3819.773	3433

	N=C	2025.00	1985.22	1871.75	1843.80	1931.443	1515
	C=O LACT.	2116.63	2211.27	2017.46	2169.02	2128.595	1659
	C=O	1998.95	2089.82	1858.77	1882.01	1957.388	1549
D1S5	OH	3456.33	3988.60	3986.17	3885.86	3829.24	3266
	N=C	2025.53	1991.61	1816.44	1926.14	1939.93	1586
	C=O LACT.	2118.28	2217.47	1937.27	2041.77	2078.698	1775
	C=O	1996.22	2087.39	1816.44	1927.78	1956.958	1686
D1S6	OH	3456.74	3987.63	3955.81	3888.67	3822.213	3236.35
	N=C	2026.58	1998.42	2025.64	1896.73	1986.843	1583
	C=O LACT.	2274.74	2347.25	2004.34	2083.28	2177.403	1739.55
	C=O	1996.96	2106.13	1852.27	1930.37	1971.433	1673.78

The observed differences may be due to the limitations of the present workstation used. As expected the AM1 method was the suitable one for the prediction of vibrational spectra as claimed by the developers. The observed data were found comparable to the reported values.

CONCLUSION

The molecular modeling was achieved using standard software and accepted methods. The insilico QSAR studies of the derivatives were performed as per accepted methods. The synthesized derivatives were found comparable to the reported derivatives prepared under conventional methods from their characterization. The activities of drug derivatives were found in accordance to the docking values and also showed comparable antibacterial studies with slight variation in activities from the conventionally prepared derivatives. The present studies supported that the microwave assisted methods can also be adopted for synthesis of suitable derivatives that have pharmacological importance with acceptable therapeutic values.

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REFERENCES:

1. Krstenansky, J.L.; Cotterill, I. Current Opinion in Drug Discovery & Development.2000, 4, 454.
2. Larhed, M.; Hallberg, A. Drug Discovery Today. 2001, 6, 406.
3. Mavandadi, F.; Pilotti, A. Drug Discovery Today.2006, 11, 165.
4. Kappe, C.O.; Angew.Chem.Int.Ed.2004, 43, 6250.
5. Kappe, C.O.; Dallinger, D. Nat. Drug. Disc. Rev.2006, 5, 51.
6. Nagariya, A.K.; et al. Journal of pharmacy Research. 2010, 3, 575.
7. Jignasa, K.S.; et al. Der Pharma Chemica. 2010, 2(1), 342.
8. More, D.H.; et al. PPJournal of Scientific & Industrial Research.2003, 62, 1024.
9. Mullasseril, A.; WJPR. 2014, 3(3), 4155.